

Establishing a Soil Health Baseline for Green Infrastructure: Sampling Natural and Semi-Natural Areas in Agricultural Landscapes

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Soil health plays a crucial role in achieving the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly Zero Hunger and Life on Land. As global efforts to meet these objectives intensify, the need for openly accessible soil data and capacity building in its use becomes increasingly urgent. The SONATA project in Serbia aims to facilitate knowledge transfer and skill development among its partners to address the impacts of climate change. The project specifically examines green infrastructure within and around agricultural landscapes, exploring how contextual green datasets can be leveraged to inform the optimal allocation of Nature-based Solutions (NbS). While beneficial, soil monitoring is far more common in intensively managed arable land than in natural habitats. The primary goal of SONATA soil study is to assess soil health within regional green infrastructure, focusing on the natural and semi-natural areas of Vojvodina. The specific objectives are to: Systematically identify representative research locations, considering the diversity of Vojvodina's natural infrastructure AND Conduct soil sampling to ensure proportional coverage of the entire study area. So, to ensure a systematic and proportional approach, we applied the LUCAS (Land Use and Coverage Area frame Survey) methodology, an EU standard for characterizing land cover and land use. Sampling area selection was conducted using machine learning techniques, incorporating spatial clustering and optimization to identify representative sites. This approach resulted in the selection of 23 forest and 39 grassland locations. At each location, we identified three sites for composite soil sampling, following the SoilBON methodology (the global Soil Biodiversity Observation Network). Each composite sample was created by mixing subsamples collected from nine points within a 30×30 m square. This process resulted in a total of 186 soil samples, distributed across four grassland clusters and four forest cover clusters. This sample collection enables us to plan and conduct a comprehensive soil health assessment based on a range of properties, including soil texture, structure, compaction, moisture, pH, nutrients, and soil microbial diversity. The resulting dataset will be integrated into the BIOS-Natural-Soil database, serving as a unique baseline dataset and a reference system for the future restoration of degraded agricultural land. Additionally, the obtained data, combined with landscape diversity indicators, will support informed spatial planning and directly contribute to the sustainable development of Vojvodina's agricultural landscape. The development and continuous expansion of this database will enhance our ability to assess Vojvodina's natural resource capacity in mitigating the effects of climate change.

Key words: soil health, natural areas, data collection, framework development